

Gamifying Software Engineering Subject to Enhance the Quality of Knowledge^{*,**}

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ABSTRACT

Gamification has been widely used in education in recent years. Gamification has been proven to be a useful tool for students, as it motivates them and helps them to learn. The lack of motivation on the part of the students and their poor perception of the importance of Software Engineering has led to the definition of SESGA. This game has been designed and carried out on third year students of the Computer Science degree. SESGA has been designed for students to improve their knowledge of static code analysis, unit testing and Git. A software engineering project was carried out in groups, in which each of the students had to perform common software development tasks. The evaluation has measured the accomplishment, challenge, competence, guidance, immersion, playfulness and social involvement of SESGA obtaining remarkable results. It has also shown that SESGA has allowed students to have better academic results and the number of failures has decreased.

1. Introduction

Every year, the number of contributions that study gamification in different fields is growing (Hamari, Koivisto and Sarsa, 2014; Zainuddin, Chu, Shujahat and Perera, 2020; Krath, Schürmann and Von Korfflesch, 2021). This type of contribution not only occurs in the educational or learning world (Krath et al., 2021), but also occurs in other areas (Hamari et al., 2014). We are going to focus on those in the educational field.

There are different definitions of gamification. According to (Caponetto, Earp and Ott, 2014), "the term gamification is generally used to denote the application of game mechanism in non-gaming environments with the aim of enhancing the processes enacted and the experience of those involved". Gamification is a strategic attempt that can turn learning into an immersive activity (Aldalur and Perez, 2023). (Perrotta, Featherstone, Aston and Houghton, 2013) indicated that learning through enjoyment and fun can be a means of introducing students to a state of *flow*. (Hunter and Werbach, 2012) said that gamification is "the use of game elements and game-design techniques in non-game contexts". According to Kapp, gamification is "using game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solve problems" (Kapp, 2012). (Ahmad, Zeshan, Khan, Marriam, Ali and Samreen, 2020) said that "gamification is an effective tool to teach tough courses at higher education level; however, group size should be taken into account for optimal classroom size and better learning experience". Apart from the definition, it must be taken into account that "playing a game is the voluntary attempt to overcome unnecessary obstacles" (Suits, 2014) and that "all games share four defining traits: a goal, rules, a feedback system, and voluntary participation" (McGonigal, 2011).

After considering the diverse definitions of gamification, a comprehensive assessment was conducted to examine the potential benefits of its implementation within the context of the Software Engineering subject. The concept of gamification encompasses the integration of game elements and mechanics into non-gaming environments. This multifaceted approach holds the promise of enhancing processes, creating immersive learning experiences, and motivating participants. In light of these definitions, the evaluation focused on how gamification could address the specific challenges associated with Software Engineering education, such as maintaining student engagement during theoretical lectures and bridging the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application.

Previously, gamification was introduced in the theoretical part of the subject (Aldalur and Perez, 2023). Scoring

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questions were introduced during the theoretical presentation. One of the objectives was to keep the students motivated during these classes. In addition, students tend not to pay attention to the theoretical aspects, as these lectures are long and not very entertaining. The students are not able to carry out the practical exercises without the concepts explained in the theoretical part. That is why it was of utmost importance for them to be attentive. This objective was achieved. However, the students still did not perceive the importance of the theoretical and practical aspects learned in the Software Engineering course. The students complied with the strictly academic aspects, since they had to pass the course, but that was all. In order for the students to learn the importance of Software Engineering, it was thought that they should complete a software engineering project in groups. Software Engineering Subject Gamification by Aldalur (SESGA) was designed to keep them motivated and to make them all participate in it.

In order for students to voluntarily want to participate in the games that are proposed to them, they must be motivated. Motivation is mandatory. Motivation is demonstrated by personal choice to engage in an activity and determines the intensity of effort and persistence in that activity (Garris, Ahlers and Driskell, 2002). Furthermore, students' needs and characteristics must be taken into account when a game is introduced (Zourmpakis, Papadakis and Kalogiannakis, 2022; Katsaris and Vidakis, 2021). This is called adaptive gamification, which "is taking care of the gamification that each particular user needs in a particular moment, tailoring the gamification to the users and contexts" (Ayastuy, Torres and Fernández, 2021).

The use of gamification in Software Engineering subjects is much more widespread (de Paula Porto, de Jesus, Ferrari and Fabbri, 2021; Alhammad and Moreno, 2018). A game has been designed for the better learning of Software Engineering, and it is important to know the opinion of the students about its accomplishment, challenge, competence, guidance, immersion, playfulness and social involvement. Moreover, it is relevant to know if SESGA has improved academic results. This is why this research questions have been designed:

- RQ1: What is the level of accomplishment obtained by students using SESGA?
- RQ2: What is the level of challenge that the students have felt during the process?
- RQ3: What is the level of competence that the students have felt during the process?
- RQ4: What is the level of guidance obtained by the students from the lecturer?
- RQ5: How involved or immersed have the students felt during the process?
- RQ6: What is the level of playfulness obtained by students using SESGA?
- RQ7: How socially involved have the students felt during the process?
- RQ8: How can academic results be better?

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Section 2 presents SESGA, the game designed and described in this work, including the motivation and how it was implemented. Section 3 describes the results obtained in the experience answering the research questions. Section 4 presents related works on gamification and compares their contribution with SESGA. Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions and future lines of action.

2. SESGA

This section describes the employed gamification process in detail, starting from its inception and covering its different phases, as well as the methodology of each one.

The experience has been developed in the Faculty of Engineering in the degree of Computer Science. 27 third-year students of the Software Engineering subject have been enrolled in the experience. This process has been carried out at the end of the semester only when all the contents of the subject have been explained to students. The course contents are as follows:

- Static Analysis: calculation of different metrics (Cyclomatic Complexity, Depth of Inheritance Tree, Maximum Nesting of Control Structures, Knot Count, etc.). Furthermore, refactoring and the use of SonarLint and Sonarqube is explained.
- Dynamic Analysis: concepts of unit testing, black and white box testing is introduced. Finally, Junit and Mocks are used to delve into these concepts.

- Git: understand git internals, branching strategy, create a repository, apply git commands to a local repository and apply git commands to a remote repository.

2.1. Inception of the experience

In recent years, many university subjects have tried to introduce new teaching methodologies: Gamification (Alhammad and Moreno, 2018), Flipped Classroom (Al-Samarraie, Shamsuddin and Alzahrani, 2020), Project-Based Learning (Chen, Lai, Lai and Su, 2022), Design Thinking (Li, Schoenfeld, diSessa, Graesser, Benson, English and Duschl, 2019)... Our university has not been an exception. The last years we have implemented the Flipped Classroom methodology in the Computer Science degree in which different subjects of different courses have been involved (Aldalur, Markiegi, Iturbe, Roman and Illarramendi, 2023). Not only we have some global experience, but also individuals as the one carried out the previous year in this same subject of Software Engineering (Aldalur and Perez, 2023).

Last year, an experience was carried out in which gamification was introduced in the theoretical classes and Discovery Learning in the practical classes. The theoretical classes were the same, but we introduced scoring questions during the presentation of the theory. The objective was to keep the students' attention in class, as they tend not to pay attention when these sessions are long. In addition, the practical classes changed their methodology, but the same exercises as in previous years were used. Through Discovery Learning, we tried to encourage students to develop their capacity for individual work and to be able to find the necessary solutions on their own. The results obtained were better than in previous years, both in terms of the final average grade and the number of failures. However, the results could be improved, and the students still did not clearly perceive the importance of Software Engineering. Students perceive the subject as one more that they must pass, but were not able to convey its importance.

2.2. Description of the experience

In order to solve this problem, SESGA was developed. First, a study was made of the different methods used in the teaching of Software Engineering. After deciding that Gamification could be the best option, SESGA was designed taking into account that we wanted students to develop to learn the importance of Software Engineering.

Once the game was designed, the students were presented with the objectives, the steps to be followed during the game, how the game would be scored and how their final mark was going to be calculated. The objectives were as follows:

- Improve Git usage
- Improve testing
- Improve software development quality

The groups that were formed were of 4 students. As there were 27 students, 6 groups of 4 members and one group of 3 members were created. For the creation of the groups, a questionnaire was passed with two questions: their final grade in the JAVA course of the second year (the project was going to be carried out in JAVA) and if they had ever used Git before the subject. For foreign students, there was a third question: whether they had learned JAVA at their universities. For the creation of the groups, the 7 students with the best grade in JAVA and the 7 worst were taken. The groups were created randomly, with one student of each type. Then the other students were introduced randomly so that in each group there was at least one student who had used Git prior to the subject. Before the start of the game, the students had to complete the following steps:

- Create a private group in Gitlab using their group name
- Create a private repository
- Invite me
- Create a Development branch
- Create one branch for each developer or member of the group

The objective of the students is to develop a 4 in a row game. The game was to be carried out in 4 development sessions and a final project evaluation session. The students were not expected to complete the entire 4 in a row game, but to be able to develop as many functions and tests of those functions as possible. Developing the basic part of the game

is uncomplicated and fast in groups of 4 members. Once finished they should think about what other functionalities could be developed (selection of tile colors, a victory marker, an avatar per player, adding turn time...). The procedure was divided in two parts: in class and after the class. The procedure of SESGA in class was as follows:

- At the very beginning of the session, development branch code scanning with SonarQube must be carried out and upload the result to Moodle.
- During the session, students must develop functions and test them, taking into account the white box condition/decision statement coverage. Every single function must have their own test. During the development, students must use SonarLint.
- Before the class ending, students must commit and push their code to the repository (each student to his/her branch).

The procedure of SESGA after the class was as follows:

- Merge all branches in to the development branch (after each session, a new student must perform this action). This branch will be analyzed with SonarQube at the beginning of the next session.

The report of the results of the analysis with SonarQube must contain the following information:

- Cyclomatic Complexity
- Number of code smells
- Number of bugs
- Test coverage percentage
- Number of vulnerabilities

After the SonarQube analysis that the students had to do of their development branch, they had to think about how to distribute the work of the session. It was mandatory for the students to try to decrease the number of cyclomatic complexity, code smells, bugs and vulnerabilities and to try to raise the percentage of code coverage. The final grade of their work depended on it because at the end of each session the lecturer had to add up the points obtained by each group. For groups of less than 4 members, the proportional result was calculated as if the group had 4 members. The purpose of this measure is not to disadvantage a group by having fewer students. The points obtained in each session by each group were as follows:

- 10 points per function
- 20 points per test taking into account the white box condition/decision statement coverage

Additionally, a classification per SonarQube report element is performed. The punctuation was as follows:

- First classified: 100 points
- Second classified: 75 points
- Third classified: 60 points
- Fourth classified: 45 points
- Fifth classified: 30 points
- Sixth classified: 15 points
- Last classified: 0 points

At the end of the sum of all the points of each of the groups, a final classification of the session was made. After the classification, each group obtained a final score for their grade for the subject. The final grade of the practice would be the average of all the marks of all the sessions. The final marks of each classified were the following:

- First classified: 10
- Second classified: 9
- Third classified: 8
- Fourth classified: 7
- Fifth classified: 6
- Sixth classified: 5
- Last classified: 4

The goal is not to fail any group if they work properly. If any group always gets the worst result, but it is detected that there is development of new functions and correct tests and moreover, they have fixed the bugs and decreased the number of code smells and vulnerabilities, the students were informed that their grade will be raised up to 5 points (lecturer personal decision).

In the last session, the students had to analyze the testing performed by the other groups. The lecturer downloaded all the projects and assigned each group to analyze another group. This assignment was done by drawing lots. Each of the groups had to write a report with each detected test error and deliver it at the end of the session. The scoring per failure was as follows:

- Missing test: 100 points
- Unnecessary test: 25 points
- Not valid test: 500 points

When a group found that a test was missing in the white box condition/decision statement coverage, it added 100 points and subtracted 100 from the group that made the mistake. Similarly, if a group created a test that was not needed and detected it, they would add 25 points and subtract 25 from the group that made the mistake. The reason for this scoring is to teach students that missing tests is more serious than having extra tests. Finally, if an invalid test was detected, 500 points were subtracted from the group that had made the mistake. On this occasion, the group that detected the error received no points. The idea is that these types of errors are simply detected by running the tests, since they give errors. Rewarding the finding of this type of error is excessive. However, it is not admissible for a group to have such an error, and so the idea was to penalize it severely.

At the end of the session, a final ranking was made with the scores of all the groups. The final score depended on the classification in the same way as in the previous sessions (10 points for the first classified and 4 points for the last classified). The final grade of each group was the average grade of each of the sessions and the final session.

3. Results

This section shows the main academic results obtained from the student of the courses 21/22 and 22/23, and it analyzes the surveys conducted to gather the opinion of the students, followed by an analysis of each of the research questions. The questions selected for the survey have been extracted from (Högberg, Hamari and Wästlund, 2019) contribution. They designed GAMEFULQUEST, a questionnaire to measure an individual or collective user's gameful experience.

3.1. Research method

Settings: The study was carried out in the Software Engineering subject in Mondragon University (Arrasate - Mondragon, Spain). This subject is part of the first semester in the third course. All participants used their own laptops during the course, and they completed their tasks using them.

Procedure: It has been explained in detail in the section 2. Finally, at the end of the experience, the participants were directed to answer an online Google questionnaire with GAMEFULQUEST questions.

Subjects: 27 students have participated in the experiment. 23 of the students were from different cities and towns of the Basque Country, 2 students were from Turkey and 2 students from Thailand. All the participants were computer

Table 1

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Accomplishment (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies							Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode	
Q1: Makes me feel that I need to complete things.	0	1	2	5	13	5	1	WA	WA	1.07
Q2: Pushes me to strive for accomplishments.	0	1	2	5	11	5	3	WA	WA	1.22
Q3: Inspires me to maintain my standards of performance.	1	3	3	4	10	5	1	WA	WA	1.5
Q4: Makes me feel that success comes through accomplishments.	0	1	3	5	11	5	2	WA	WA	1.21
Q5: Makes me strive to take myself to the next level.	0	1	2	6	9	8	1	WA	WA	1.15
Q6: Motivates me to progress and get better.	0	0	3	4	8	9	3	WA	A	1.17
Q7: Makes me feel like I have clear goals.	1	1	4	5	7	8	1	WA	A	1.44
Q8: Gives me the feeling that I need to reach goals.	0	1	1	5	9	8	3	WA	WA	1.19

science degree students.

Instrument: A Google Forms questionnaire were used to collect the user's experience in the evaluation. This questionnaire has been responsible for collecting all the information related to tables 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7. The responses were collected on a 7-point Likert scale (Likert, 1932). The reason for the use of 7-Point Likert Scale is that (Högberg et al., 2019) designed GAMEFULQUEST questionnaire based on this scale. The results have been limited to percentages. Through the analysis of these data, we have been able to obtain the tendency on the opinion of the students in each one of the questions in which they have been asked.

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the sample and to evaluate the participants' experience. Moreover, the standard deviation value was calculated to confirm statistically the data collected. Results of this analysis are shown in all tables (tables 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7). The frequencies have been described as Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree, (D), Weak Disagree (WD), Neither agree nor disagree (N), Weak Agree (WA), Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA). The states that the average of the responses is higher than a value of 4 (N value in the tables), corresponding to a favorable level of accomplishment, challenge, competition, guidance, immersion playfulness and social experience in the questions evaluated.

RQ1: What is the level of accomplishment obtained by students using SESGA?

Table 1 shows the results to this research question. The aim of this research question is knowing the demand or drive for successful performance, goal achievement, and progress of students (Högberg et al., 2019). The results of all the questions obtained a median of WA. Similarly, the mode was WA for all the questions except for questions 6 and 7, where the mode was A. In the responses, it can be observed that the majority of the students voted that they agree with each of the statements on accomplishment. The worst rating was given to question 3 in which 7 students (25.92%) disagreed that SESGA inspires them to maintain their standards of performance. However, 16 students (59.26%) agreed with this statement. For all other questions, between 2-5 students disagree and between 16–22 students agree. 22 people agree that SESGA makes them need to reach or meet the objectives (Q8) and furthermore it motivates them to progress and get better (Q6). With these two questions (and also taking into account the others), it can be affirmed that the accomplishments obtained by the students have been achieved with SESGA in addition to being motivated by the system of the game itself.

Standard deviation measures the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of values. The lower the value, the more values are near the average value. Most values are close to the 1 value, which means that most subjects' opinion are similar.

The results affirm that the students feel that with SESGA they have been able to achieve the accomplishments set at the beginning and have been motivated to achieve them.

Table 2

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Challenge (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies							Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode	
Q1: Makes me push my limits.	0	1	3	5	9	6	3	WA	WA	1.29
Q2: Drives me in a good way to the brink of wanting to give up.	1	2	1	7	9	6	1	WA	WA	1.39
Q3: Pressures me in a positive way by its high demands.	0	2	2	4	12	4	3	WA	WA	1.32
Q4: Challenges me.	1	0	3	4	11	5	3	WA	WA	1.36
Q5: Calls for a lot of effort in order for me to be successful.	0	0	2	5	7	10	3	WA	A	1.12
Q6: Motivates me to do things that feel highly demanding.	1	1	3	5	11	5	1	WA	WA	1.33
Q7: Makes me feel like I continuously need to improve in order to do well.	0	1	2	5	11	7	1	WA	WA	1.12
Q8: Makes me work at a level close to what I am capable of.	1	1	3	4	11	5	2	WA	WA	1.41

RQ2: What is the level of challenge that the students have felt during the process?

Table 2 presents the student's results about this question. The goal of this research question is to check if students experience a great effort in order to be successful (Högberg et al., 2019). The results on challenge for all the questions show that the mode and median were WA except for question 5 whose mode is A. This indicates that the results obtained are very similar to those obtained in RQ1. In question 5, only 2 people (7.4%) disagree with the statement (the lowest in the whole series of questions) and 20 (74.07%) agree (the highest in the whole series). The students believe that it took a lot of effort to achieve their goals. This shows that the game was not trivial and that students needed to work hard to achieve what they initially set out to do. For questions 6 and 8, 5 students (18.52%) disagreed, the highest of the series. They believe that SESGA does not motivate them to do things that feel highly and demanding, and it does not make them work at a level close to what they are capable of. This percentage of students is too low to consider this a problem. In addition, 17 (Q6) and 18 (Q8) agree with this statement.

The standard deviation results are very similar to RQ1. In this case all the results are very close to 1, even closer than in the previous case, so there is no significant difference in the opinion of the students.

The results on challenge show that SESGA carried out has been challenging, i.e., it has not been trivial. Therefore, the effort required by the students to meet the objectives was elevated.

RQ3: What is the level of competence that the students have felt during the process?

Table 3 illustrates the result of the level of competence. The idea with this research question is to check the experienced rivalry towards one or more students (self, other person, service, or group) to gain a scarce outcome that is desirable for all students (Högberg et al., 2019). In the case of competition, the results show higher values than for the two previous research questions. In this case, for most of the questions, the median is WA except for question 4 where the median is A. However, most of the modes are A except for questions 1 and 7 where the mode is WA and for question 4 the mode is SA. The only SA mode of all the questions in the questionnaire was for question 4 in which most students feel they should or want to be in first place. That is a very important part of the game, it makes them feel a goal and a motivation (valued in RQ1). Despite this, it is not the question in the series with the most people disagreeing. In question 7, only 2 students (7.4%) disagree that they need to win to succeed. Except for questions 1 and 2, 20 students (74.07%) agree on their need and desire to win. This shows that SESGA has been an appropriate method to encourage competition among students.

The highest standard deviation of the whole questionnaire is given in questions 1 and 5 of this series. These are the only 2 questions whose standard deviation is greater than 1.5. In any case, the values are very close to 1, which means that there are no significant differences.

Table 3

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Competition (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies							Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode	
Q1: Feels like participating in a competition.	1	2	2	4	8	7	3	WA	WA	1.57
Q2: Inspires me to compete.	0	2	4	5	6	9	1	WA	A	1.38
Q3: Involves me by its competitive aspects.	1	0	3	3	9	10	1	WA	A	1.31
Q4: Makes me want to be in first place.	0	0	3	4	5	7	8	A	SA	1.37
Q5: Makes victory feel important.	1	1	1	4	7	7	6	WA	A	1.55
Q6: Feels like being in a race.	0	0	3	4	7	9	4	WA	A	1.22
Q7: Makes me feel that I need to win to succeed.	0	0	2	5	8	6	6	WA	WA	1.24

Table 4

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Guidance (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies							Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode	
Q1: Makes me feel guided.	1	2	6	7	8	2	1	N	WA	1.35
Q2: Gives me a sense of being directed.	1	3	4	9	7	3	0	N	N	1.3
Q3: Makes me feel like someone is keeping me on track.	1	3	3	7	9	4	0	N	WA	1.36
Q4: Gives me the feeling that I have an instructor.	0	1	2	7	8	6	3	WA	WA	1.27
Q5: Gives me the sense I am getting help to be structured.	0	3	4	7	5	7	1	N	A	1.42
Q6: Gives me a sense of knowing what I need to do better.	1	2	2	6	7	8	1	WA	A	1.47
Q7: Gives me useful feedback, so I can adapt.	0	0	1	3	8	13	2	A	A	0.93

The best results of the questionnaire are given in the SESGA competition. The students see the need and desire to come in first place, as they consider victory to be important.

RQ4: What is the level of guidance obtained by the students from the lecturer?

Table 4 shows the result to this question. The objective of this research question is to check if students have been properly guided on how (including what and when) to do, and on how to improve the target behavior (Högberg et al., 2019). This is the research question with the worst results. In the case of the guidance, we have obtained results whose median is neutral (N) in 4/7 questions. In addition, one of the modes is also neutral (N). This is the only table in which this neutral value appears as median or as mode. One of the objectives was that they should work on their own and that in case of doubt they should ask the lecturer. Question 2 is the worst rated for that reason, the students did not feel that they had a person guiding them (the only question with the mode and the neutral median (N)). Question 1 is the one in which more students disagree (33.33%) because the students did not feel that they were guided. However, question 7 shows that the advice given by the lecturer (they have always had the right and opportunity to ask their doubts and problems) has been useful for the students (85.18% of the students agree).

In this case also, the standard deviation shows values very close to 1, so there is no significant difference between results.

The worst results of the questionnaire have been obtained in this topic. The guidance method used in SESGA has been the worst evaluated. Although there are more students agreeing than disagreeing, the guidance should be improved in future editions.

Table 5

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Immersion (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies								Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode		
Q1: Gives me the feeling that time passes quickly.	0	0	0	3	8	11	5	A	A	0.92	
Q2: Grabs all of my attention.	0	0	1	2	6	12	6	A	A	1.02	
Q3: Gives me a sense of being separated from the real world.	0	0	1	3	5	12	6	A	A	1.06	
Q4: Makes me lose myself in what I am doing.	0	0	3	3	6	12	3	A	A	1.17	
Q5: Makes my actions seem to come automatically.	0	0	2	6	5	9	5	A	A	1.24	
Q6: Causes me to stop noticing when I get tired.	0	0	2	4	4	10	7	A	A	1.24	
Q7: Causes me to forget about my everyday concerns.	0	1	2	3	5	12	4	A	A	1.3	
Q8: Makes me ignore everything around me.	0	1	3	4	5	9	5	A	A	1.42	
Q9: Gets me fully emotionally involved.	0	1	4	4	6	9	3	WA	A	1.38	

RQ5: How involved or immersed have the students felt during the process?

Table 5 exhibits the answers to this question. The purpose of this research question is to detect if all attention is taken over, and the student experiences being absorbed in what they are doing, while having a sense of being dissociated from the real world (of time, of own actions, or of space) (Högberg et al., 2019). Regarding immersion, the results obtained were outstanding. For all the medians and modes of all the questions a result of agree (A) has been obtained except for the median of question 9 whose value is Weak Agree (WA). Question 9 is the one in which more students disagreed (18.5%) because these students did not feel emotionally involved. In general, the students feel totally involved in their activities. They recognize that they forget their daily problems (77.77%), that they ignore what is around them (70.37%), that time passes quickly (88.88%).... This makes the proposed scoring system make the students feel involved and motivated (as described in RQ1).

As in the previous cases, the standard deviation obtains values very close to 1.

Immersion has been the best rated by the students. With SESGA the students were completely immersed in their activities, they feel that time passes quickly and forgot about everyday concerns.

RQ6: What is the level of playfulness obtained by students using SESGA?

Table 6 display the results of the students to this question. The goal of this research question is to verify if students are involved in voluntary and pleasurable behaviors that are driven by imagination or exploration, while being free from or being under spontaneously created rules (Högberg et al., 2019). In the case of playfulness, the results obtained are very similar to those of RQ1 and RQ2. For all the modes and medians of all the questions, the result has been obtained is of Weak Agree (WA). All the questions in this research question had between 3 and 5 students disagreeing (between 11.11% and 18.5%). These percentages are very low. 16 to 19 people agreed with each of the questions (59.26% and 70.37%). These percentages show that students perceive SESGA as playful. The best rated by the students is that they feel that SESGA gives them an overall playful experience and makes them feel like they discover new things. This second point is very important and one of the reasons for the creation of SESGA. The students, despite learning the software engineering aspects, did not see its importance. When students discover new things, they discover the importance of the concepts taught in the subject. The students also feel that they need to be creative, they need to explore things and that their curiosity has been encouraged.

The standard deviation of the results obtained in this research question are very similar to the previous ones, close to 1 and none exceed 1.4.

The playfulness results obtained show that thanks to SESGA the students have had to use their imagination, that they have explored, encouraged their curiosity and learned new concepts.

Table 6

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Playfulness (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies							Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode	
Q1: Gives me an overall playful experience.	0	1	2	5	11	6	2	WA	WA	1.17
Q2: Leaves room for me to be spontaneous.	0	1	3	7	8	6	2	WA	WA	1.25
Q3: Taps into my imagination.	1	1	3	5	12	4	1	WA	WA	1.31
Q4: Makes me feel that I can be creative.	1	1	2	6	11	4	2	WA	WA	1.35
Q5: Gives me the feeling that I explore things.	0	1	4	5	12	4	1	WA	WA	1.15
Q6: Feels like a mystery to reveal.	1	1	3	5	10	6	1	WA	WA	1.36
Q7: Gives me a feeling that I want to know what comes next.	0	0	3	5	12	6	1	WA	WA	1.01
Q8: Makes me feel like I discover new things.	0	1	3	5	9	8	1	WA	WA	1.19
Q9: Appeals to my curiosity.	1	1	1	7	9	7	1	WA	WA	1.32

Table 7

Results of the level of participants' agreement about Social Experience (Strongly disagree, SD; Disagree, D; Weak disagree, WD; Neither agree nor disagree, N; Weak agree, WA; Agree, A; Strongly agree, SA).

Questionnaire	Frequencies							Descriptive stats.		Dv.
	SD	D	WD	N	WA	A	SA	Median	Mode	
Q1: Gives me the feeling that I'm not on my own.	0	1	0	6	11	7	2	WA	WA	1.07
Q2: Gives me a sense of social support.	0	0	1	5	7	11	3	A	A	1.04
Q3: Makes me feel like I am socially involved.	0	0	0	3	9	7	8	A	WA	1.02
Q4: Gives me a feeling of being connected to others.	0	0	1	3	9	7	7	A	WA	1.11
Q5: Feels like a social experience.	0	0	0	4	7	11	5	A	A	0.97
Q6: Gives me a sense of having someone to share my endeavors.	0	0	0	5	11	7	4	WA	WA	0.96
Q7: Influences me through its social aspects.	0	0	1	5	9	9	3	WA	A	1.03
Q8: Gives me a sense of being noticed for what I have achieved.	0	0	1	4	8	11	3	A	A	1.01

RQ7: How socially involved have the students felt during the process?

Table 7 presents the result to this research question. The purpose of this question is to verify that students are involved and help one each other during the activity (Högberg et al., 2019). The results of the SESGA social experience have been excellent. Of the 8 questions asked, in 5 of them the median was agree (A) and in 3 weak agree (WA). Similarly, agree (A) was the top 4 times and weak agree (WA) 4 times. In this research question we found that only 1 student disagreed with only 5 of the questions (Q1, Q2, Q4, Q7 and Q8). In all the other questions, there was not a single student who disagreed with these statements. These are the lowest values obtained in the entire questionnaire. This reinforces the idea that SESGA has obtained terrific results in social experience. The questions with the best results were Q2, Q5 and Q8 whose medians and modes were agree (A). The students have felt that SESGA gives them a sense of social support, they feel like a social experience and gives them a sense of being noticed for what they have achieved. The students have felt supported by the group work, they have felt help from their peers. This may be because the students know that the final grade depends on the results of all members of the group.

The standard deviation for this question obtained the most similar results. None of the questions exceeded the value of 1.1 for question 4. This shows that the differences in the answers are not significant at all and that the students have the same opinion about the social experience.

The social experience obtained outstanding results by obtaining the lowest number of students in disagreement with respect to the other items by far. The students felt supported by their peers at all times.

Table 8

Student results of the courses 20/21, 21/22 and 22/23

20/21			21/22			22/23		
#Students	AVG mark	#Fails	#Students	AVG mark	#Fails	#Students	AVG mark	#Fails
32	5,22	12	41	6,06	9	27	6,53	4

RQ8: How can academic results be better?

Table 8 shows the number of students, the average mark of all students, and the number of students that did not pass each year. The 20/21 academic year was the control group with 32 students. They obtained an average grade of 5.22 and 12 of these students did not pass. These results are very similar to the previous years. Next year, during the 21/22 academic year, 41 students were enrolled in Software Engineering. This year, gamification in the theory classes and the Discovery Learning during the exercises were implemented (Aldalur and Perez, 2023). The average grade was 6.06 and the number of failures was 9. Now, this academic year (22/23), a final gamified practice has been introduced. The average grade has been 6.53 and 4 students fail the subject.

Table 8 illustrates how an improvement of 0.84 in the average grade among students after applying gamification and Discovery Learning, which is an outstanding improvement between 20/21 and 21/22 academic years. Additionally, the table shows an improvement of 0.47 points after implementing SESGA between the 21/22 and 22/23 academic years. In total, there has been an improvement of 1.31 points in two academic years. Furthermore, the number of fails have been reduced from 12 to 4. Taking into account only the difference between the last two academic years (21/22 and 22/23), results confirm that SESGA allows enhancing academic results among students. On the other hand, we have the number of failures. In the 21/22 academic year, 9 students failed out of 41 (21.95%) while this year, 4 students failed out of 27 (14.81%). These data shows that the number of failures was reduced by 7.14%, a percentage that SESGA has improved academic results among students.

Results confirm that SESGA has enhanced academic results because the average grade has increased and the number of failures has decreased.

3.2. Threats to validity

Our limitation affects the number of students. It is considered that 27 students is an important and representative number without nonetheless, 23 of them belong to the same group, Basque Country citizens. The remaining 4 students are not a representative number to draw conclusions between students from the Basque Country and students from other countries. The study should be replicated in universities in different countries and check if the same results are obtained.

Additionally, another noteworthy consideration is the potential impact of the subject lecturer presenting the questionnaire to the students. While efforts were made to minimize this influence, such as providing the questionnaire before the final exam, it is possible that students who were aware of not passing the exam might have inclined towards lower scores in their responses. Conversely, those who believed they had passed might have provided more favorable ratings and additionally, students who considered they had obtained a good mark in the activity. This awareness bias should be considered when interpreting the questionnaire results.

4. Related work

If we review the literature, we can find different contributions that have been applied in the subject of Software Engineering. In these contributions, we find different methodologies applied in this subject. For example, (Morais, Ferreira and Veloso, 2021) detected that students had difficulties in learning subjects related to modeling and programming. To solve this problem, they implemented a project-based learning experience. The aim was to improve student engagement and learning outcomes achievement and allow students to experience the need for the software development lifecycle. They designed 8 different tasks that students had to carry out. They defined 6 evaluation criteria based on their work and effort to achieve them. The number of passes increased by more than 20%, a higher mark than the one achieved with SESGA. In any case, we are talking about pass rates that were below 50% and are now around 70%. In another case, (Palacin-Silva, Khakurel, Happonen, Hynninen and Porras, 2017) involved 29 students in the

Software Engineering course. Their goal was to improve the students' skills in software design and testing. They designed the 16 weeks of the course in 8 sessions of 3 hours and 4 mentoring sessions. First they did the project planning, thought about the requirements, then the code development, testing, maintenance and presentation. They emphasize that the motivation of the students increased so much that there was no more absenteeism in class. The evaluation was based on the personal opinions of lecturers and students. There are no questionnaire data or academic results to compare with. For the software engineering course, Discovery Learning is used to encourage the search for information and the individual work of each student (Aldalur and Perez, 2023). In addition, the theoretical classes are gamified by introducing gamified questions in order to keep the students' attention in class. In this case the number of failures decreases and the average grade is increased as it happens with SESGA. The rest of the evaluation assesses the structure of the WebQuests used for Discovery Learning and their opinion about them. On the other hand, they value the gamification tool (Wooclap) and the gamification itself. The results in all of them are positive. The comparison with SESGA is complicated as the same aspects are not asked. In any case, students feel more motivated and eager to attend class thanks to the gamification of the classes as with SESGA.

Gamification has not been used exclusively in Software Engineering, as in the previous contribution. There are other subjects in which it has been used. We can look at the case of (Portela, 2020) who designed a proposal to gamify Computer Science subjects in addition to using other methodologies such as Flipped Classroom. At the time of COVID, the idea was to improve the motivation and the presence of the students in the sessions, especially in the online sessions. The theoretical sessions were in Flipped Classroom format. Then the practical sessions try to meet various objectives designed by the lecturer. In addition, Kahoot sessions were added to encourage discussion among the students. The results show that absenteeism was reduced even in online classes. There are no results about the academic results and the students' opinion about the method used, which complicates the possibility to compare his results. In another contribution, (López Carrillo, Calonge García, Rodríguez Laguna, Ros Magán and Lebrón Moreno, 2019) applied gamification in two different courses involving 150 students in the first year and 183 students in the second year. To gamify the sessions, they used Kahoot and Class Dojo. Their objective was to eliminate negative prejudices, fear and rejection attitudes towards science. Using gamification, they managed to get 96% of the students to attend class, reducing absenteeism. However, they were not able to conclude whether students were able to learn more. (García-Cabot, García-Lopez, Caro-Alvaro, Gutierrez-Martinez and de Marcos, 2020) implemented the gamification in the Master degree of Software Engineering for the Web with 27 students. They involved two different groups (control group vs. gamified group) and compared the results obtained from both. The gamified group obtained better academic results. This process was accomplished over two weeks with 5 teaching hours each. The students' sensation was that gamification was beneficial to learn the basic concepts of the matter. The application used for gamification enhanced the relationships between students. Furthermore, it made learning more participatory and motivating for the students. In the process, each assignment was scored, and a ranking was generated with each student's score. Similar to SESGA, academic results increased. However, we do not know how the challenge, immersion or guidance of this experience were.

In the literature, we can verify that gamification has been used to improve the subject of Software Engineering. The results obtained are different in addition to the games obtained to achieve them. If we ask ourselves if it is worth implementing gamification for software testing, the answer is yes. (de Jesus, Paschoal, Ferrari and Souza, 2019) demonstrated through a game they designed the impact of gamification in software testing. The results were very positive. The experimental group was more motivated and obtained a higher performance. There are numerous of contributions that implemented gamification in Software Engineering subject. (Dal Sasso, Mocchi, Lanza and Mastrodicasa, 2017) implemented a framework that is an extension of Taje. With this framework, they have adapted an existing game to their needs. This game focuses on obtaining medals or merits for each of the participants. The objectives of this framework for the authors are to improve the quality of bug reports, stimulate the participation of the community and ease the fixing process. By means of a template, they describe to the students the activity, the analysis, the implementation and the testing to be done. Despite the focus on testing, they only work on fixing bugs. SESGA tries to make the students learn how to fix bugs, but it also tries to make them improve coverage, decrease the number of code smells, learn how to use Git better, etc. SESGA is more complete. Unfortunately, the evaluation does not provide information that can be compared with SESGA. In addition, this work does not provide us with information on whether the students have obtained better academic results and thus cannot be compared with SESGA. (Sungkaew, Lungban and Lamhya, 2022) developed GDSE, a model for game development. The GDSE model is introduced for game developers as a framework to create better games in terms of usability enhancement, game experience and educational value. The 22 students involved in the course were required to design different games, which they had to evaluate and test. All

games have the same objective: finding the way to a certain destination, and then those were called "Find the Way". The games were to be evaluated based on the following criteria: challenge, competence, flow, immersion, positive affect, negative affect and tension. These criteria are very similar to those used to evaluate SESGA. However, for each of these criteria, only one question was asked, which gives less information than in the case of SESGA. The authors conclude that the academic results are better, but they do not talk about the number of failures and the average grade. (Costa and Oliveira, 2020) carried out another case of gamification in Software Engineering. Their goal is to encourage students to do exploratory testing. In a similar way to the previous one, this time they have also designed a game in which students get merits and medals. This work focuses only on testing, unlike SESGA, which delves into other aspects as well. The students have managed to obtain more than 70% of the achievements. In the case of SESGA, we could not count the number of achievements because there were none. The objective was always to develop and improve the metrics of the previous static analysis with SonarQube. The evaluation does not show us if the academic results have improved among the students, it only focuses on the achievements obtained by the students in the game.

5. Conclusions and future work

This paper presents the SESGA method used to gamify the Software Engineering subject of the third academic year of the Computer Science degree. During 2022/23 academic year, 27 students have participated in this initiative. The experience has been carried out with the intention of motivating students and demonstrating with facts the importance of Software Engineering in the development of applications.

This experience has been evaluated with the GAMEFULQUEST questionnaire, a questionnaire designed by (Högberg et al., 2019) to measure an individual or collective user's gameful experience. The results obtained have been excellent. The aspect to improve is the guidance of the students, as they have felt that they have not been guided by the lecturer towards their objectives. In spite of this, they show their gratitude to the lecturer, highlighting that when they have asked him doubts, he has clarified them correctly and helps them to continue with the project. The other results show that SESGA has fostered the social experience as the students have been supported and helped by their peers. The immersion was terrific as the time was short, and they forgot their problems, and the competition was great as the students wanted to win the game. This may be because their final grade depended on their performance. The students also highlighted that it was an attractive challenge as they were motivated to complete the tasks even more than expected and this made them learn new things. Finally, the students emphasize in the achievement that they have understood the need to complete the tasks and achieve the objectives initially set.

In the future, the desire is that the students feel more guided during the process. This has been the aspect worst valued by the students and therefore, it would be necessary to analyze how other lecturers guide their students and apply it in SESGA. In addition, it has been thought that instead of developing a game like 4 in a row, the students should develop some application that improves the knowledge in another subject. The Operating System's lecturer considers that the process followed in SESGA would fit in his subject. In this case, the idea is to pose a problem (PBL, Problem Based Learning) to the students and that they are able to solve it by implementing a code. The evaluation system would be the same as the one used in SESGA as well as the process in class.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Iñigo Aldalur Methodology, Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Resources, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data is provided as supplementary material, and will be publicly available upon acceptance.

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